

Mapping Research Topics on Financial Reports in Sharia Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around Financial Statements in Islamic Financial Institutions. The research was conducted from 2005 to 2022, by searching national journals indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword "Financial Statement". Based on the search results, there were 131 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to Financial Statement is divided into 10 clusters and 185 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 5 main themes related to Financial Statements in Islamic Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Financial Statements, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic Financial Institutions

Introduction

Financial reports play an important role for stakeholders because they are a source of information for company decision making. The functions of preparing financial reports include: (1) Management can make future decisions; (2) Investors who invest in shares can decide to hold, add, or sell company shares; and (3) The government can calculate the duties that must be paid by the company.

In previous research, banks are financial institutions whose mission is to store funds from the public and return them to society. The performance of conventional bank financial institutions and sharia financial institutions can be seen from their financial reports. Therefore, financial reports are a reflection of the company's health condition. Financial reports at conventional and sharia financial institutions have differences in the types of financial reports. Sharia banks record their activities and present them in financial reports which are prepared periodically. Presenting appropriate and accurate financial reports is important for Islamic banks, because it can be used as an indicator of improving bank performance and as material for reflection to make wise decisions. Apart from that, sharia banking is also required to present other financial reports, such as cash flow statements, reports of changes in financial position (statements). of financial position changes), as well as notes to financial reports (notes to financial statements). The main objective of presenting financial reports in Islamic banking is to provide accurate and transparent information about the financial performance of Islamic banks to stakeholders, such as customers, investors, regulators and the public in general.

Scientific publications on financial reports in sharia banking continue to experience growth, which can be seen from 131 studies in the last 14 years which can be found on the Garuda website. Therefore, financial reports have an important role for sharia banking. This research aims to build a map of research and development of sharia banking financial reports over the last 14 years using bibliometrics VOSviewer and literature review studies.

Literature Review

Financial reports on Sharia Financial Institutions are reports containing financial information about sharia banking operational, financial and investment activities during a certain period which are prepared based on sharia principles. Financial reports in Islamic banking include several main reports, such as the financial position report (balance sheet), income statement and statement of changes in equity. These reports provide an overview of the financial performance of Islamic banks, including assets, liabilities, equity, income and operational costs during a certain period.

Bibliometric studies are a branch of science that analyzes and evaluates scientific publications and related information. It involves the use of statistical and informatics methodologies to assess the production, citation, and dissemination of knowledge in scientific literature. Bibliometric studies can be used to measure the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions and scientific fields, as well as to understand interactions and relationships between scientific fields and publications. It can also help in the identification and evaluation of trends and issues in the scientific literature.

VOSviewer is bibliometric software used for visualization and analysis of scientific publication data. It allows users to visualize citation, co-citation, and co-word analysis data in the form of graphs and diagrams that are intuitive and easy to accept. VOSviewer has an easy-to-use user interface and can be used together with data coming from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. It allows users to visualize and analyze publication data effectively and efficiently.

Studies Literature review is a process that includes identification, evaluation, and synthesis of results from previous research on a specific topic. It aims to provide an overview of trends, issues, and advances in related fields and assist in understanding how previous research influences future research developments and directions.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is Financial Reports at Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Financial Reports originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords " Sharia Financial Report " and "Sharia Financial Statement" for the entire year (20 05 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on literature review studies.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Financial

Reports in Sharia Financial Institutions

The results of searching scientific publications regarding financial reports in Sharia Financial Institutions from 2005 to 2022 show an increase in publications every year, especially in 2019 with 16 articles.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding financial reports by year

Year of Publication	Number of Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Articles
2005	1	2013	5	2018	17
2009	1	2014	4	2019	19
2010	2	2015	7	2020	16
2011	1	2016	10	2021	22
2012	5	2017	8	2022	13
Total 131					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In Table 2, there are 9 affiliates/institutions that publish the most research articles regarding Financial Reports in Sharia Financial Institutions. The Accounting Journal Collection is the largest publishing institution that publishes research results regarding Financial Reports, namely 17 articles.

Table 2. Data on Institutions and Journals Publishing Financial Report Journal Articles

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Accounting journal	17
Economic Journal	6
Journal of Community Service	6
Journal of Islamic Economics and Sharia Banking	5
Journal of Accounting Scientific Studies, Faculty of Economics, UNTAN	4
Journal of Sharia Economics	4
Journal of Islamic Accounting and Finance	3
Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance	3
Journal of Economics and Business of Islam	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 3 shows that out of a total of 131 published research articles regarding Sharia Financial Reports on the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital), the most productive researcher is Rizky Yuniar Romadhon from the Muhammadiyah University of Malang who wrote 3 journal articles.

Table 1. Researcher Productivity Regarding Financial Reports

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Rizky Yuniar Ramadhon (Muhammadiyah University of Malang)	3
Adam Prayogo (Sebi Islamic Economics College), Ibnu Qizam (Muhammadiyah University of Malang), Esti Nurhikmah Prastika (Muhammadiyah University of Pekajangan)	2
Muhammad Iqbal (UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya), Rizky Yuniar (UIN Alauddin), Riskiyatur (UIN Malang), Landes Yuanda (UIN Suka Kalijaga), Iwan Budiyo (UIN Walisongo Semarang), Waluyo Masjono (UIN Jakarta),	1

Rustamunadi (UIN Sultan Maulana Hasanudin Banten),
 Ulfi Kartika (UIN Malang), Rifqah Alifiyyah (UIN Alauddin),
 Sri Wahyuni (UIN Alauddin), Nawirah Ula (UIN Malang),
 Asbi Amin UIN Sunan Gunung Jati Bandung)

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding Financial Reports in Sharia Financial Institutions

Article search results on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) are exported to RIS (Research Information System) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Visualization of a network map of research developments around Financial Reports

Source: Data processed using software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

the co-word map network visualization of the development of research on financial reports in Sharia Financial Institutions, divided into 10 clusters and 185 topics, are as follows:

- Cluster 1, the red color consists of 40 topics, namely: ability, according, balance sheet, bopo, capital, company, customer, dalat collection, debt, deposit, documentation, equity, fact, fdr, field, financial institution, financial performance, financial ratio, financial ratio analysis fund, good corporate governance, income statement, institution, Islamic bank, Islamic financial institute, liability, liquidity object, performance, profit, profitability, prospective customer, provision, ratio, risk profile, roa, roe, sfas, sharia, cooperative total assets.
- Cluster 2, the green color consists of 28 topics, namely: aspect, asset, bank bjb syariah Cirebon, baznaz, disclosure, effort, entity, financial statement, implementation, internal control, interview, Islamic financial report, level, managers perception, observation, operation, the purpose of this research, person, process, qualitative research, regulation, rule, secondary data, sharia, sharia entity, source, stakeholder.
- Cluster 3, light blue color consists of 24 topics, namely: change, corporate governance, discretionary accrual, earnings management, external pressure,

faithful representation, financial stability, financial statement fraud, financial statement, financial target, fraud, fraudulent financial start independent variable, indication, industry, Islamic banking, Islamic commercial tire, OJK, period, population, questionnaire, Sharia bank, Sharia commercial bank, value.

- Cluster 4, yellow consists of 22 topics, namely: abnormal return, accounting, activity, application, author, benefit, business, disclosure index, financial report, insurtech, investor keywords, knowledge, member, preparation, problem, report, service, sharia principle, significant influence, startup, term.
- Cluster 5, purple consists of 20 topics, namely: audit committee, sharia commercial banks, BPRS, effects, factors, financial reporting, Indonesia, Islamic banking financial statement, Islamic work ethics, leverage multiple linear regression, quality, respondent, role, Indonesian bank certificate, sharia financial account, sharia supervisory board, significant effect, understanding.
- Cluster 6, dark blue color consists of 16 topics, namely: account, bmt, bsm, cash flow, cash flow statement, component, data collection technique, entity, financial information, financial management, PSAK, SFAS no 101, research method, temporary syirkah fund, year, zakat.
- Cluster 7, orange color consists of 14 topics, namely: accounting standards, sharia audit, collection, extent, Islamic accounting standards, Islamic corporate government, Islamic financial statement, perception presentation, quality percentage, quantitative percentage, quantitative approach, sharia financial statement, student, sharia.
- Cluster 8, brown consists of 10 topics, namely: comparison, conventional banking, conventional banking, differences, fees, income, non-halal income, operating income, transactions.
- Cluster 9, the color pink consists of 6 topics, namely: Islamic banking, compliance, efficiency Islamic bank financial report, obedient, research.
- Cluster 10, pink consists of 5 topics, namely: independent sharia banking, composition, financial accounting standards, financial position, statement.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Disclosure of Financial Reports in Sharia Financial Institutions

Literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 20 problems surrounding the disclosure of financial reports at Sharia Financial Institutions, namely:

First, the sharia value added report. The sharia added value report in sharia banking financial reports can reflect the contribution made by sharia banks to the economy and society as a whole, apart from purely financial aspects. This report is in line with sharia principles which emphasize the importance of social justice and community welfare. The following are several elements that are usually contained in sharia value added reports in sharia banking financial reports: (1) Sharia income and costs; (2) Operational and social activities; (3) The added value generated; and (4) Social indicators.

Second, earnings management. Profit management in sharia banking financial reports should not be carried out because it is contrary to sharia principles which adhere to justice, transparency and accountability. Islamic banking must follow sharia principles in all aspects of its business, including financial reporting. However, if earnings management practices occur in Islamic banking financial reports, this can be done in less honest ways, such as manipulating income or costs, changing the value of assets or liabilities, and using incorrect accounting practices.

These practices will lead to inaccurate financial reports and can mislead Islamic banking stakeholders.

Third, preparing and presenting financial reports based on Maqashid Syariah. The following are several important steps in preparing and presenting financial reports in Islamic banking based on Maqashid Syariah: (1) Determining the Company's Goals and Targets; (2) Determine the Sharia Accounting Principles Used; (3) Preparing Comprehensive Sharia Financial Reports; (4) Presenting Financial Reports with Transparency and Openness; and (5) Conduct Regular Audits of Financial Reports.

Fourth, supervision. Supervision of financial reports in sharia banking is carried out by several parties, including: (1) Financial Services Authority (OJK); (2) Sharia Supervisory Board/DPS; (3) Public Accountant; (4) Internal Audit.

Fifth, PSAK 101, 102, 105, 107, 109, 112. Financial reports in sharia banking must be prepared based on sharia financial accounting standards (SAKS) which refer to Sharia Accounting Principles (PAS) and Financial Accounting Standards (SAK) that have been generally applicable. The following is an explanation of each PSAK:

- (1) PSAK 101: Presentation of Sharia Financial Reports. PSAK 101 determines the procedures for presenting sharia financial reports which include the presentation of the balance sheet, profit and loss report, report on changes in equity, and cash flow report. Sharia financial reports must be prepared based on sharia accounting principles and must include relevant and material information. Sharia banking financial reports must include information regarding sharia contracts used by the bank in carrying out its operations, such as Mudharabah, Musyarakah, Murabahah contracts, etc.
- (2) PSAK 102, 105, 107, 109, 112: Murabahah, Mudharabah, Wakalah, Ijarah and Profit Sharing Accounting. This PSAK regulates the recognition, measurement and disclosure of these contractual transactions. Sharia banking financial reports must include information regarding the amount of financing provided using these contracts. Apart from that, the financial report must also include information regarding the income obtained by the bank from these contract transactions.

Sixth, comparison between the Income Statement Approach and the Shari'ate Value Added Statement/SVAS. Income Statement Approach, which is an approach that refers to conventional financial reports used by non-shariah companies, where the profit and loss report or income statement provides information about the company's income, costs and net profit. However, in sharia banking, income and cost components must be classified in accordance with sharia principles, for example, income from usury or interest may not be recognized as sharia banking income. Shari'ate Approach Value Added Statement (SVAS), which is an approach based on the concept of added value generated by the company, namely the value produced by the company after taking into account the contributions of all company stakeholders, including shareholders, employees, customers and the community. This approach refers to sharia principles and provides a broader view of sharia company performance than the Income Statement Approach. In Islamic banking, the SVAS approach is often used in conjunction with the Income Statement approach to provide a more complete picture of company performance. The SVAS approach provides more detailed information about the impact of company activities on society and the environment, while the Income Statement approach provides more specific information about the company's financial performance.

Seventh, the difference with conventional. The following are some of the main differences: (1) Basic principles, namely sharia banking is based on the principles of Islamic sharia, which prohibits usury (interest) and speculative transactions and requires profit sharing; (2) Products and services, namely sharia banking only offers financial products and services that comply with sharia principles, such as

mudharabah (profit sharing), musyarakah (joint venture), and murabahah (buying and selling with a markup); (3) Accounting and reporting, namely sharia banking must use sharia accounting in carrying out its financial reporting; (4) Audit, namely sharia banking must follow different audit standards from conventional banking, where auditors must understand sharia principles and evaluate whether the bank has complied with these principles; (5) Use of funds, namely sharia banking has an obligation to use the funds they receive ethically and in accordance with sharia principles, such as halal and socially responsible investments.

Eighth, sharia accounting. The principles of sharia accounting consist of several things, such as the absence of usury, transactions must be carried out fairly, honestly and transparently, and there is no element of speculation. Sharia accounting also has accounting standards that are different from conventional accounting, such as sharia accounting standards (SAS) and sharia financial accounting standards (SAKS).

Ninth, presentation of Qardhul Hasan's financial accounting reports. The presentation of Qardhul Hasan accounting financial reports involves recording and reporting Qardhul transactions Hasan carried out by sharia banking. Financial reports must include relevant and reliable information, such as the amount of the loan granted, loan term, success rate of loan repayment, and other necessary information.

Tenth, training and assistance in preparing financial reports, which is very important in sharia banking to ensure that financial reports are presented correctly in accordance with sharia accounting principles. Training and mentoring can be carried out by internal or external parties, such as auditors or sharia financial consultants. Training and mentoring can also help sharia banks implement appropriate sharia accounting standards and ensure that their financial reports are accurate and trustworthy.

Eleventh, disclosure of non-halal income. In sharia banking financial reports, disclosure of non-halal income should be done separately and clearly from halal income. This is important to do because sharia banking aims to avoid transactions that violate sharia principles, including transactions involving non-halal sources of income. Several things that can be done in disclosing non-halal income in sharia banking financial reports include: (1) Grouping income; (2) Explanation of types of income; (3) Proportion of non-halal income to total income; (4) Actions to avoid non-halal income.

Twelfth, tax accounting. Tax accounting in sharia banking financial reports refers to sharia accounting standards (SAS) and tax regulations applicable in each country. The following are several things that need to be considered in tax accounting in sharia banking financial reports: (1) Selection of tax accounting methods; (2) Income recognition; (3) Determination of tax burden; (4) Deferred taxes; and (5) Tax risk management.

Thirteenth, income statement. The profit and loss report in Islamic banking financial statements is similar to the profit and loss report in conventional banking financial statements. However, there are some differences in terms of valuation and transaction recognition. The following are several important points regarding profit and loss statements in Islamic banking financial statements: (1) Income from margins; (2) Income from profit-sharing; (3) Operational costs; (4) Provision costs and losses; (5) Tax.

Fourteenth, sources of benevolent funds, include: donations from sharia banks, alms, proceeds from waqf management, returns of productive benevolent funds, fines, non-halal income. In financial reports, sharia banking will usually include the amount of social funds collected and social funds that have been distributed during a certain period. Apart from that, sharia banking will also record costs related to managing social funds, such as administration costs and distribution

costs. Sharia banking must also ensure that the management of social funds is carried out in a transparent and accountable manner.

Fifteenth, the use of benevolent funds, includes: productive benevolent funds, donations, and other uses for the public interest. In sharia banking financial reports, the use of benevolent funds must be recorded in a separate section with clear notes regarding the purpose and amount of use. Apart from that, the use of benevolent funds must also be in accordance with sharia principles regulated by the Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI) or the relevant sharia fatwa body.

Sixteenth, IFRS and AAOIFI standards. The following are several important points that must be considered in preparing sharia banking financial reports in accordance with IFRS and AAOIFI standards: (1) Sharia banking financial reports must reflect sharia financial principles, such as the principle of profit and loss sharing, mudharabah principles, murabahah principles, and the principle of wakalah. In addition, Islamic banking financial reports must also reflect accounting principles that are commonly used throughout the world. (2) Islamic banking financial reports must include a balance sheet, which lists assets, liabilities and equity. Sharia banking assets can include financing, investments, savings, and others. Sharia banking obligations can include customer funds, bank debt, and others. Islamic banking equity can include share capital, reserves and retained earnings. (3) Sharia banking financial reports must include a profit and loss report that includes income, costs, net profit and net loss. Sharia banking income can include income from financing, investment, etc. Sharia banking costs can include operational costs, financing costs, and others. (4) Sharia banking financial reports must include cash flow reports that include cash receipts and cash disbursements from operational, investment and financing activities. (5) Sharia banking financial reports must be accompanied by notes to the financial reports that include additional information such as accounting policies, explanations of banking activities, and information about business risks and opportunities. (6) Sharia banking financial reports must be prepared in clear and easy to understand language. This is important so that financial reports can be understood by all interested parties, including customers, investors and regulators.

Seventeenth, tax amnesty. In sharia banking financial reports, tax amnesty must be recorded in the profit and loss report and balance sheet. In the profit and loss report, Islamic banks must include the amount of tax forgiven and also the amount of tax that has been paid. Meanwhile, in the balance sheet report, Islamic banks must include taxes that have not been paid before the tax amnesty program was implemented and taxes that have been paid after the tax amnesty program took effect.

Eighteenth, the effect of financial report announcements on stock returns. The announcement of financial reports can have a significant influence on company stock returns, because financial reports provide important information about the company's financial performance, including revenue, profits and cash flow. If the financial report shows that the company has good financial performance, then this can cause an increase in demand for the company's shares, which can encourage an increase in share prices and an increase in stock returns. Conversely, if financial reports show poor financial performance, this can cause a decrease in demand for the company's shares, which can lead to a decrease in share prices and a decrease in stock returns.

Nineteenth, consolidated financial statements. Consolidated financial reports in sharia banking involve combining the financial reports of the parent bank and subsidiary or affiliated entities owned by the bank. Consolidated financial reports present financial information covering all of the company's business and operations, thereby providing a more complete and accurate picture of the financial position, operating results and cash flows of sharia banks. Several things that must be

considered in preparing consolidated financial reports in sharia banking include: (1) Identifying subsidiary and affiliated entities that must be included in the consolidated financial statements; (2) Determine the appropriate consolidation method; (3) Ensure that the consolidated financial statements comply with applicable accounting standards; and (4) Present relevant additional information.

Twentieth, Fraud Diamond analysis. Fraud Diamond is a framework used to analyze factors that can influence the occurrence of fraud. This framework consists of four main factors, namely pressure, opportunity, rationalization and capability. In the context of sharia banking, Fraud Diamond analysis can be used to identify and analyze factors that can trigger fraud in the sharia banking system.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Determinant Variables of Financial Report Fraud in Sharia Financial Institutions

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 3 determinant variables of financial statement fraud in Sharia Financial Institutions, namely:

First, there is pressure, including: Financial Stability, External Pressure, Personal Financial Need, Financial Target, Effective Monitoring, Sharia Compliance, Change in director, Frequent number of CEO's Picture. The explanation is as follows: (1) Financial Stability, which can influence fraudulent financial reports in sharia banking because companies that are financially unstable tend to be more easily tempted to commit fraud; (2) External Pressure, which can influence fraudulent financial reports in sharia banking because companies may feel forced to commit fraud in order to meet the expectations or requirements of external parties; (3) Personal Financial Need or personal financial needs, which can influence fraudulent financial reports in sharia banking because the individual may feel forced to commit fraud to meet their personal needs; (4) Financial Target or financial targets, which can influence fraudulent financial reports in sharia banking because companies may feel forced to commit fraud to achieve predetermined financial targets; (5) Effective Monitoring or effective monitoring, which can influence fraudulent financial reports in sharia banking because if supervision is not effective, fraud can occur without being detected; (6) Sharia Compliance or sharia compliance, which can influence fraudulent financial reports in sharia banking because if the company does not comply with sharia principles properly, the company may be tempted to commit fraud; (7) Change in Director or change of directors, which can affect fraudulent financial reports in sharia banking because changing directors can disrupt company stability and trigger internal conflicts which can trigger fraudulent practices; (8) Changing the CEO or Chief Executive Officer in sharia banking can influence financial statement fraud positively or negatively. Periodic CEO changes can help avoid fraudulent practices, because they can ensure effective rotation and supervision in company management.

Second, there are opportunities, including: Nature of Industry, Ineffective Monitoring. The explanation is as follows: (1) Nature of Industry, which can influence the occurrence of fraudulent financial reports in sharia banking because competitive pressure and intense competition in the industry can trigger unethical behavior and fraudulent practices; and (2) Ineffective Monitoring or ineffective supervision, namely the lack of effective supervision can enable fraudulent practices and abuse of power by internal parties in the company.

Third, rationalization. This factor can influence the occurrence of fraudulent financial statements in sharia banking because justification or the search for reasonable reasons can make fraud perpetrators feel that their actions are legitimate or reasonable.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Determinant Variables for the Quality/Soundness of Financial Reports in Sharia Financial Institutions

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 21 variables determining the quality/soundness of financial reports at Sharia Financial Institutions, namely:

First, the audit committee. The audit committee can help improve the quality of financial reports by conducting more thorough and in-depth internal audits, thereby minimizing the possibility of errors or fraud in financial reporting.

Second, the Sharia Supervisory Board/DPS. DPS is responsible for ensuring that all sharia banking products and services comply with sharia principles. DPS also has the authority to supervise and evaluate the performance of sharia banking management. With strict supervision, DPS can ensure that sharia banking financial reports are protected from fraud or manipulation.

Third, Islamic work ethic. The Islamic work ethic encompasses Islamic moral and ethical principles, including honesty, integrity, and social responsibility. Islamic work ethics can motivate sharia banking employees to act professionally and comply with ethical standards in carrying out their duties. This can help prevent fraudulent practices or other violations that can affect the quality of financial reports.

Fourth, Islamic Corporate Governance/ICG. In the context of financial reporting, ICG can help ensure that sharia banking financial reporting is transparent, accountable and consistent. Sharia compliance covers all aspects of a business, including banking operations, products and services. In terms of financial reporting, Sharia Compliance can help ensure that financial reports are prepared in accordance with applicable sharia principles and accounting standards with applicable sharia principles.

Fifth, Sharia compliance. Compliance with sharia principles shows that the bank is socially responsible and has a good reputation. This affects the quality of financial reports by showing transparency and accountability in financial reporting.

Sixth, earnings sustainability. Profit sustainability is important in maintaining investor and creditor confidence and ensuring banking continuity. Sustainability of high profits can strengthen the quality of financial reports by showing that banks have the ability to fulfill their financial obligations.

Seventh, profitability. Good profitability indicates healthy and efficient performance. Islamic banking that produces good profits tends to be more stable and has a better reputation. This can strengthen the quality of financial reports by demonstrating the banking ability to fulfill financial obligations and maintain good performance.

Eighth, Information and Communication Systems/GIS. A good SIK can help sharia banking in obtaining accurate, timely and integrated data and information. With a good SIK, the accounting and financial reporting process can be carried out more easily and efficiently. This can affect the quality of financial reports because the financial reports produced can be more accurate, complete and timely.

Ninth, fraud. Fraud or cheating in the presentation of financial reports can result in the resulting financial reports being inaccurate or not reflecting the actual financial condition of sharia banking. This can have a negative impact on the quality of financial reports, and can cause financial losses and a bad reputation for Islamic banking.

Tenth, independent commissioner. Independent commissioners play a role in supervising and controlling the performance of sharia banking management. By having a good independent commissioner, the monitoring and control process can be carried out more effectively, thereby reducing the risk of fraud or violations in the presentation of financial reports. This can have a positive impact on the quality of financial reports because the resulting financial reports can be more accurate, reliable and relevant.

Eleventh, leverage. High leverage can make it difficult for a company to fulfill its financial obligations and can reduce the quality of financial reports. However, if leverage is used wisely, for example to expand a business, it can increase the company's profitability and the quality of financial reports. Therefore, the effect of leverage on the quality of financial reports in Islamic banking depends on how wisely it is used.

Twelfth, Fee Based Income. Fee Based Income can improve the quality of financial reports if the company can obtain income from these sources stably and consistently, because this income can increase the company's profitability and can help the company to fulfill its financial obligations.

Thirteenth, term of office of the Board of Directors. Long terms of office can have both positive and negative impacts on the quality of financial reports. On the one hand, a long term of office can increase the expertise and experience of board members in managing the company and improve the quality of financial reports. On the other hand, a long term of office can reduce the ability of directors to maintain creativity and innovation in facing the challenges faced by the company.

Fourteenth, company size. The larger the company, the more complex the financial reports and the more transactions that occur. Therefore, large companies usually have more mature accounting and reporting processes. However, it is important to remember that the quality of financial reports does not only depend on the size of the company, but also on the quality of the accounting information system and management's ability to manage the company's finances.

Fifteenth, feasibility of providing financing. If a company provides financing to customers who are unfit or do not have the ability to pay, then credit risk and the possibility of bad credit will increase. This can affect the quality of financial reports because financial reports reflect the company's financial condition which is also influenced by credit performance.

Sixteenth, Sharia audit standards. Sharia audit standards guarantee that sharia principles have been applied in the company's financial management and that the financial reports presented have been tested and verified by independent auditors. This can improve the quality of financial reports and provide confidence to stakeholders that the financial reports presented are accurate and reliable.

Seventeenth, level of relevance. Relevant information will provide a clear picture of the company's financial position and performance. In sharia banking, relevant information must also consider sharia aspects, such as compliance with sharia principles in financial transactions. Therefore, the higher the level of relevance of information in financial reports, the better the quality of financial reports in sharia banking.

Eighteenth, faithful representation. Financial reports that have an accurate representation will provide a clear and objective picture of the company's financial position and performance. Accurate representation will also increase stakeholder confidence in the company's financial reports. Therefore, the more accurate the representation in financial reports, the better the quality of financial reports in Islamic banking.

Nineteenth, employee knowledge. Good knowledge will ensure that financial reports are prepared well and meet applicable accounting standards. In addition, employee knowledge of sharia principles is also very important in ensuring that financial reports reflect compliance with sharia principles. Therefore, the better the employee's knowledge of accounting and sharia principles, the better the quality of financial reports in sharia banking.

Twentieth, optimization of Financial Technology. By adopting new and innovative technology, financial processes can be carried out more efficiently and accurately. Fintech can also help Islamic banking to reduce the risk of human error in processing financial data, thereby increasing the reliability of financial reports.

Apart from that, fintech can also speed up the presentation of financial reports by speeding up the process of collecting, processing and reporting data.

Twenty-first, Internal Control System/SPI. SPI helps sharia banking to maintain the integrity and reliability of financial reports by minimizing the risk of human error, fraud or legal violations in the financial data processing process. SPI also helps sharia banking to identify, analyze and resolve problems related to financial processes.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Financial Report Ratios in Sharia Financial Institutions

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 17 financial report ratios in Sharia Financial Institutions, namely: (1) Capital/Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR; (2) Asset quality, including: Quality of Productive Assets/KAP, Non-Performing Financing/NPF; (3) Management, including: Net Foreign Exchange Position/NOP, Net Profit Margin/NPM; (4) Profitability/ Earnings includes: Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Operational Expenses to Operational Income/BOPO, Net Returns/NI ratio, Gross Profit Margin/GPM; (5) Liquidity ratios, including: Current Ratio, Cash Ratio, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR; (6) Market risk/ Interest Expense Ratio/IER; (7) Solvency ratios, including: Debt to Asset Ratio/DAR, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER; (8) Activity ratios, including: Fixed Assets Turnover and Total Assets Turnover; (9) Profitability ratios, including: Profit Margin On Sales, Return On Investment/ROI; (10) Days Sales in Receivable Index/DSRI; (11) Gross Margin Index/GMI; (12) Assets Quality Index/AQI; (13) Sales Growth Index/SGI; (14) Depreciation Index/DEPI; (15) Sales, General, and Administrative Expenses Index/SGAI; (16) Leverage Index/LEV; and (17) Total Accruals to Total Assets/TATA.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Financial Report Models in Sharia Financial Institutions

literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 7 models of financial reports in Sharia Financial Institutions, namely:

First, CAMEL method. The CAMEL method is one of the methods used to analyze bank financial health. The abbreviation CAMEL is the initials of the five assessment factors, namely Capital (capital), Assets Quality (asset quality), Management (management), Earnings (profit), and Liquidity (liquidity). This method is used to assess the financial health of Islamic banking by paying attention to these five factors.

Second, the RGEC method. The RGEC method stands for Profitability, Growth, Efficiency and Asset Quality. This method is used to analyze the financial performance of sharia banking by paying attention to these four factors. The profitability factor refers to the bank's ability to generate profits from invested capital, growth refers to the growth of the bank's income over time, efficiency refers to the bank's ability to manage operational costs effectively, and asset quality refers to the quality of the bank's credit portfolio.

Third, the Kirkpatrick model. The Kirkpatrick model is a performance evaluation model that consists of four levels of evaluation: reaction, learning, behavior, and results. This model can be applied to evaluate the effectiveness of training and development, as well as to analyze the financial performance of Islamic banking by paying attention to aspects of reaction and learning. This model considers customer and employee perceptions and assessments, as well as the impact of training on improving financial performance.

Fourth, Accounting Software application. Accounting software applications can play a very important role in producing accurate and timely financial reports for Islamic banking. Some of the ways in which accounting software applications can

influence sharia banking financial reports include: (1) Accounting software applications can help manage financial data more efficiently, thereby enabling sharia banking to process transactions more quickly and accurately; (2) With the right accounting software application, sharia banking can monitor their finances in real-time; (3) Accounting software applications can help produce accurate financial reports quickly and easily; (4) With accounting software applications, financial data can be managed more easily and more transparently; and (5) Accounting software applications can help sharia banking to make better decisions based on accurate and up-to-date financial data.

Fifth, SAK-ETAP. Sharia banking as an entity without public accountability is required to apply SAK-ETAP in preparing its financial reports. However, because sharia banking has different characteristics and operating principles from conventional banking, there are several differences in the application of SAK-ETAP in sharia banking, including: (1) Sharia banking refers to sharia principles in carrying out its operational activities, such as the principle of profit sharing (profit sharing) and buying and selling principles; (2) Sharia banking must also report its activities and performance separately for sharia products and conventional products; and (3) Sharia banking must provide additional disclosures in its financial reports regarding the sharia principles applied, such as disclosure regarding the sharia products offered, disclosure regarding the composition and role of the sharia supervisory board, as well as disclosure regarding the method for calculating profit sharing.

Sixth, Horizontal and Vertical Models. In this case, analysts compare numbers in financial statements from previous years to see trends and changes over time. In its application to sharia banking, the Horizontal Model can provide information about asset growth, revenue performance, operational efficiency and company profit margins over time. Meanwhile, the Vertical Model is used to compare financial ratios and percentages of each item in the financial statements in one accounting period. In this case, analysts pay attention to the comparison between each item in the financial statements and total assets or income. In its application to sharia banking, the Vertical Model can provide information about the company's financial structure and the comparison between asset, debt and capital components. Vertical Models can also help in assessing a company's financial health through financial ratios such as core capital ratios, capital adequacy ratios, and liquidity ratios.

Seventh, Common Size analysis. There are several things that need to be considered when applying Common Size analysis to Islamic banking financial reports. The following are several steps that can be taken to apply Common Size analysis to sharia banking financial reports: (1) Identifying sources of income in sharia banking is important because sharia banks operate based on sharia principles which prohibit usury, where sharia bank income comes from a share of business results. (profit and loss sharing) or fixed profit (fixed profit) from sharia transactions; (2) Common Size analysis must focus on sharia aspects in sharia banking financial reports; (3) Islamic banks use different accounting accounts from conventional banks; and (4) Islamic banking is subject to different regulations and accounting standards than conventional banks.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- Number of research publications around Financial Reports at Sharia Financial Institutions during the period 2005 to 2022, shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 131 research articles, which come from national journals indexed by Sinta.

- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is the Accounting Journal Collection, with 17 articles.
- The most productive researcher is Rizky Yuniar Romadhon from the University of Muhammadiyah Malang who wrote 3 journal articles.
- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding Financial Reports in Sharia Financial Institutions are divided into 10 clusters and 185 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 40 topics, cluster 2 consists of 28 topics, cluster 3 consists of 24 topics, cluster 4 consists of 22 topics, cluster 5 consists of 20 topics, cluster 6 consists of 16 topics, cluster 7 consists of 14 topics, cluster 8 consists of 10 topics, cluster 9 consists of 6 topics, and cluster 10 consists of 5 topics.
- Based on the literature review, there are 5 main research themes, namely: (1) Disclosure of financial reports; and (2) Determinant variables of fraud in financial reports; (3) Determinant variables for the quality/soundness of financial reports; (4) Financial report ratios; and (5) Financial report model.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the literature review study can be explained in a more complex way.

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